

1 A genomic approach for targeted chemotherapy in cytogenetically unstable disease.

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7 We used the iso7q chromosomal anomaly found in hepatosplenic T cell lymphoma (HSTCL) as a model
8 for discovery of factors associated with cytogenetic instability in cancer.

9 Citations

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